

Chemical speciation of ternary complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with L-glutamine and succinic acid in CTAB-water mixtures

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Abstract : Chemical speciation of ternary complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with L-glutamine and succinic acid have been studied pH metrically in the concentration range of 0.0–2.5% w/v of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) in aqueous solutions maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol L⁻¹ (NaCl) at 303.0 K. Alkalimetric titrations were carried out in the presence of different relative concentrations (M : L : X = 1 : 2 : 2, 1 : 4 : 2, 1 : 2 : 4) of metal (M) to L-glutamine (L) to succinic acid (X) with sodium hydroxide. Stability constants of ternary complexes were calculated and various models were refined with MINIQUAD75. The best-fit chemical models were selected based on statistical parameters and residual analysis. The predominant species detected were ML₂X, MLX, MLXH and MLXH₂ for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}. Extra stability of ternary complexes compared to their binary complexes was believed to be due to electrostatic interactions of the side chains of ligands, charge neutralization, chelate effect, stacking interactions and hydrogen bonding. The species distribution with pH at different compositions of CTAB and plausible equilibria for the formation of species were also presented.

Keywords : Speciation, ternary complexes, L-glutamine, succinic acid, CTAB.

Introduction

The main endogenous source¹ of L-glutamine (Gln) is de novo synthesis² in striated muscle via the enzyme glutamine synthetase. Gln serves as a vehicle for transporting ammonia in a nontoxic form from peripheral tissues to visceral organs where the ammonia³ can be excreted as ammonium ion (kidneys) or converted to urea (liver). Gln itself acts as a buffer and also produces⁴ bicarbonate, which functions as a buffer in the body to neutralize excess blood and muscle acids generated especially during heavy anaerobic exercises. It is also utilized for the growth and differentiation of the neural cells⁵. It is often depleted in stress states, such as malignancy⁶. Gln plays an important therapeutic role in the prevention of damage to normal tissues including peripheral nerves during chemotherapy⁷. Succinic acid (Suc) is involved in citric acid or tricarboxylic acid (TCA) cycle and glyoxalate cycle. Hence, the speciation studies of ternary complexes of Gln and Suc with Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} in CTAB-water mixtures have been reported in this paper.

Results and discussion

Complex equilibria :

A preliminary investigation of alkalimetric titrations of mixtures containing different mole ratios of Gln and Suc in presence of mineral acid and inert electrolyte inferred that MLXH, MLX, ML₂X and MLXH₂ species are formed for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}. log β values along with standard deviation (SD) values are presented in Table 1.

CTAB acts as a denaturant of macromolecules by interacting with peptide groups and the dielectric constant of the medium decreases with increasing concentration of surfactant⁸⁻¹⁰. Hence, the stability of the charged species decreases with increasing CTAB content because the species will be destabilized. The linear decrease also indicates the dominance of electrostatic forces over non-electrostatic forces on the complex equilibria.

Stability of ternary complexes :

The formation of mononuclear, unprotonated binary and ternary complexes from a mixture of metal ion (M)

Table 1. Best-fit chemical models of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of L-glutamine-succinic acid in CTAB-water mixtures

Temp. = 303 K, ionic strength = 0.16 mol L⁻¹

% w/v	log β _{mlxh} (SD)			
	1110	1111	1112	1210
Co ^{II} (pH range 2.0-9.0)				
0.0	8.12(13)	14.13(30)	18.99(21)	11.88(10)
0.5	7.84(18)	14.34(20)	18.54(41)	11.39(15)
1.0	7.08(13)	13.56(17)	18.04(23)	10.54(8)
1.5	7.61(17)	14.00(25)	18.84(14)	11.34(8)
2.0	7.29(23)	13.61(40)	18.91(12)	11.17(12)
2.5	7.81(22)	13.86(34)	18.83(15)	11.83(13)
Ni ^{II} (pH range 2.0-9.0)				
0.0	9.09(19)	14.71(20)	19.79(10)	13.40(13)
0.5	8.55(7)	13.95(15)	18.49(18)	12.92(8)
1.0	8.43(9)	13.64(22)	18.39(14)	12.59(9)
1.5	8.49(12)	13.77(24)	18.65(12)	12.82(13)
2.0	9.73(18)	-	20.39(7)	14.46(10)
2.5	9.83(13)	15.14(17)	19.86(10)	14.54(14)
Cu ^{II} (pH range 2.0-6.0)				
0.0	11.73(7)	16.33(8)	20.13(10)	17.79(7)
0.5	11.28(5)	15.70(6)	19.49(6)	17.49(5)
1.0	10.71(5)	15.12(5)	18.80(7)	16.59(5)
1.5	10.27(7)	14.80(7)	18.60(7)	16.06(9)
2.0	10.41(8)	15.02(8)	19.13(5)	16.06(15)
2.5	10.89(10)	15.45(9)	19.49(5)	17.25(7)

and primary (L) and secondary (X) ligands can be shown as the equilibria given in eq. (1).

The difference in stability (Δ log K) for the two reactions ML with X and M(aq) with X is compared with that calculated purely on statistical grounds. Eq. (2) can be formulated based on the properties of the cyclic systems reported earlier¹¹⁻¹⁵, from which it is clear that both the ligands in the ternary complex influence mutually to the same extent.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Delta \log K &= \log K_{MLX}^{ML} - \log K_{MX}^M \\
 &= \log K_{MLX}^{MX} - \log K_{ML}^M \\
 &= \log K_{MLX}^{ML} - K_{ML}^M - K_{MX}^M \quad (2)
 \end{aligned}$$

The values of Δ log K calculated by assuming Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} ions to form octahedral complexes with Gln and Suc, are found to be higher than those expected on statistical grounds. The extra stability of the ternary complexes might be due to the interactions outside the coordination sphere, like formation of hydrogen bonds between the coordinated ligands. Also a similar stabilizing effect may like-wise be exerted by the electrostatic interactions between non-coordinated, charged groups of the ligands like -NH₃⁺ of L-glutamine and -COO⁻ of succinic acid¹⁶.

Distribution diagrams :

A perusal of the distribution diagrams (Fig. 1) reveals that at very low pH the concentrations of mixed ligand complexes are less than those of protonated ligands. The concentrations of the ternary species are increased with increasing pH. The protonated ternary species, MLXH and MLXH₂ are distributed at lower pH and the unprotonated ternary species, MLX and ML₂X at higher pH. Higher concentrations of the ternary species than those of binary species indicate the higher stability of the former. The ternary species exist in the pH range 2.0-9.0 for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and 2.0-6.0 for Cu^{II} respectively. The formation of the complex species can be represented by the following equilibria. The charges of the species are omitted for clarity.

Biological relevance of present study :

The presence of CTAB in aqueous solution consider-

Fig. 1. Species distribution diagrams of ternary complexes of Gln and Suc with (A) Co^{II} , (B) Ni^{II} and (C) Cu^{II} in 2.5% w/v CTAB-water mixture.

ably decreases the dielectric constant of the medium and these solutions are expected to mimic the physiological conditions. The species refined and their relative concentrations represent the possible forms of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} ions in the presence of glutamine and succinate residues under the present experimental conditions.

Experimental

Solutions of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} chlorides (0.1 mol L^{-1}) have been prepared by dissolving GR grade (Merck, India) salts in triple distilled water. Aqueous solutions of Gln and Suc (Merck, India) have also been prepared. To increase the solubility of Gln and Suc and to suppress the hydrolysis of metal salts, mineral acid concentration in the above solutions has been maintained at 0.05 mol L^{-1} . CTAB (Merck, India) was used as received. 0.2 mol L^{-1} hydrochloric acid (Qualigens, India) and 0.4 mol L^{-1} sodium hydroxide (Qualigens, India) were prepared. 2 mol L^{-1} sodium chloride (Qualigens, India) was prepared to maintain the ionic strength in the titrand. To assess the errors that might have crept into the determination of the concentrations, the data have been subjected to analysis of variance of one way classification (ANOVA). The strength of alkali has been determined using the Gran plot method¹⁷.

Apparatus :

The titrations have been carried out in the medium containing varying concentrations of CTAB maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol L^{-1} with sodium chloride at 303.0 K. A Systronics μ pH system (model 362) (readability 0.001) has been used. The glass electrode has been equilibrated in a well stirred CTAB-water mixture containing inert electrolyte. The effect of variations in asymmetry, liquid junction potential, activity coefficient, sodium ion error and dissolved carbon dioxide on the response of glass electrode are accounted for in the form of correction factor¹⁸ which was computed from the simulated acid-base titration data calculated by SCPHD program¹⁹. Correction was applied to the pH meter dial reading by using correction factor. Titrations of strong acid with alkali have been carried out at regular intervals to check complete equilibration of the electrode. The calomel electrode has been refilled with CTAB-water mixture of equivalent composition as that of the titrand. In each of the titrations, the titrand consisted of 1–3 mmol of mineral acid in a total volume of 50 cm^3 . Titrations have been carried out in presence of different relative concentrations (Table 2) of metal (M) to Gln (L) and Suc (X) with 0.4 mol L^{-1} NaOH.

Modeling strategy :

The best-fit chemical models consisting of stoichio-

Table 2. Total initial concentrations of ingredients (in mmol) for mixed-ligand titrations in CTAB-water mixtures

% w/v	TMO			TLO		M : L : X
	Co ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Gln	Suc	
0.0	0.1998	0.1998	0.1996	0.4007	0.3984	1 : 2 : 2
				0.8014	0.3984	1 : 4 : 2
				0.4007	0.7967	1 : 2 : 4
0.5	0.1998	0.1998	0.1996	0.4007	0.3983	1 : 2 : 2
				0.8014	0.3983	1 : 4 : 2
				0.4007	0.7967	1 : 2 : 4
1.0	0.1998	0.1998	0.1996	0.4007	0.3983	1 : 2 : 2
				0.8013	0.3983	1 : 4 : 2
				0.4007	0.7966	1 : 2 : 4
1.5	0.1998	0.1998	0.1996	0.4006	0.3983	1 : 2 : 2
				0.8013	0.3983	1 : 4 : 2
				0.4006	0.7966	1 : 2 : 4
2.0	0.1998	0.1998	0.1996	0.4006	0.3983	1 : 2 : 2
				0.8013	0.3983	1 : 4 : 2
				0.4006	0.7966	1 : 2 : 4
2.5	0.1998	0.1998	0.1996	0.4007	0.3983	1 : 2 : 2
				0.8013	0.3983	1 : 4 : 2
				0.4007	0.7966	1 : 2 : 4

[NaOH] = 0.4 mol L⁻¹; V₀ = 50.0 cm³; Temp. = 303 K; ionic strength = 0.16 mol L⁻¹; mineral acid = 1–3 mmol.

metric coefficients and logarithm of stability constants (log β) were arrived at by using the computer program MINIQUAD75²⁰. Some heuristics were followed in refining stability constants²¹ and validating models²². The formation constants for acid-base equilibria and those for binary metal complexes of Gln and Suc were fixed in the refinement of mixed ligand stability constants using MINIQUAD75.

References

- G. Biolo, R. Y. Fleming, S. P. Maggi and R. R. Wolfe, *Am. J. Physiol. Endocrinol. Metab.*, 1995, **268**, E75.
- N. Nurjhan, A. Bucci, G. Perriello, M. Stumvoll, G. Dailey, D. M. Bier, I. Toft, T. G. Jenssen and J. E. Gerich, *J. Clin. Invest.*, 1995, **95**, 272.
- W. Wiley and M. D. Souba, *Ann. Surgery*, 1993, **218**, 715.
- T. C. Welborne, *Am. J. Nutr.*, 1995, **61**, 1058.
- M. Tetsuya and M. Nobuhiko, *Med. Sci. Res.*, 1989, **17**, 425.
- J. M. Lacey and D. W. Wilmore, *Nutr. Rev.*, 1990, **48**, 297.
- W. S. Wang, J. K. Lin, T. C. Lin, W. S. Chen, J. K. Jiang, H. S. Wang, T. J. Chiou, J. H. Liu, C. C. Yen and P. M. Chen, *Oncologist*, 2007, **12**, 312.
- A. K. Singh and D. Manjula, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **71**, 635.
- E. H. Cordes, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1978, **50**, 617.
- C. A. Bunton, G. Cerichelli, Y. Ihara and L. Supulveda, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **101**, 2429.
- R. Griesser and H. Sigel, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, **9**, 1238.
- R. B. Martin and R. Prados, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 1665.
- H. Sigel, *Chimia*, 1967, **21**, 489.
- H. Sigel, K. Becker and D. B. McCormick, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta*, 1967, **148**, 655.
- H. Sigel, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1975, **14**, 394.
- M. S. Babu, G. N. Rao, K. V. Ramana and M. S. P. Rao, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. India*, 2003, **73A**, 173.
- G. Gran, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1988, **206**, 111.
- M. S. Babu, G. N. Rao, K. V. Ramana and M. S. P. Rao, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 1334.
- G. N. Rao, PhD Thesis, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam, India, 1989.
- P. Gans, A. Sabatini and A. Vacca, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1976, **18**, 237.
- G. N. Rao and R. S. Rao, *J. Indian Council Chem.*, 1992, **8**, 12.
- B. B. V. Sailaja, T. Kebede, G. N. Rao and M. S. P. Rao, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 155.